

NFDI4Earth

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Review of pilot support and interaction with the academy

Felix Cremer

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Executive summary

This document captures the support NFDI4Earth Measure 2.5 “Advancing Tools” offered for the first round of pilots of the NFDI4Earth project and the interaction with the Academy.

Contents

1 Pilot support	1
1.1 Consulting	1
1.2 Development support	1
2 Review	1
3 Interaction with the Academy	1

1 Pilot support

1.1 Consulting

We participated in the first pilot meeting to explain the concept of a data cube and to investigate which data handling solutions are used in the pilot studies. There were 14 pilot studies in total in the first round of which five used data cube technologies or were interested in working with data cubes. These pilots used data cubes for model data and satellite observation data. We met with three interested pilots to further discuss the use of data cubes in general and the use cases of data cubes and their advantages and disadvantages.

1.2 Development support

Fruitful interactions have taken place with the NFDI4Earth pilot “Statistical Learning to assess factors underlying environmental changes”. They transferred the application of new statistical methods to a data cube framework and approached us with several support requests. We could solve most of the technical questions the pilot posed to us and contributed to its success in creating their product.

The following list of GitHub issues was solved in relation to the support of this pilot:

- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/159>
- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/192>
- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/216>
- <https://github.com/JuliaDataCubes/YAXArrays.jl/issues/237>

2 Review

We participated in the review of the new round of pilots and also in the selection of the academy fellows. In this review we focused especially on the advancement of data handling tools and how they could help to increase the FAIRness of data in the Earth System Sciences.

3 Interaction with the Academy

To disseminate the usage of data cube technologies to early career scientists we are currently planning to participate in the Academy hackathon with a data cube use case that will enable the Academy fellows to work with data cube in a confined environment and to get hands-on

experience in the handling of data cubes. The main focus of this hackathon challenge is to show the usage of data cubes for the analysis of large raster data. Hereby we show how data can be prepared as a data cube. This preparation of the data can enhance the reusability since the analysis via data cube tools can be automated and applied on new datasets easily.